

IRISCC

D3.1

IRISCC Training and Knowledge Exchange Plan

Disclaimer: Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Abstract

Keywords

hackathon, knowledge, learning, training, webinar, workshop

This document outlines the knowledge exchange and training plan of IRISCC, to be implemented over the lifetime of the project. The plan describes a series of knowledge exchange and training activities, categorised in terms of target audiences, the format in which the activity is conducted and the delivery medium. For each of the planned activities, the deliverable includes its objectives, timings, needed prerequisites to achieve the activity goals and means to measure the impact of each of the activities.

Revision History

Version	Date	Description	Author/Reviewer
V 0.1	18/12/2024	First Draft	Jaana Bäck (UH) Beñat Olascoaga (UH)
V 0.2	15/01/2025	First Draft Revision	Alexandre Belleflamme (FZJ) Magdalena Brus (EGI.eu) Yin Chen (EGI.eu) Veronika Gaube (BOKU) Päivi Haapanala (Luke) Klaus Steenberg Larsen (UCPH) Pasquale Pagano (CNR) Christian Pagé (CERFACS) Sabine Philippin (CNRS) Mariana Salgado (ICOS ERIC) Charles Troupin (ULiege)
V 0.3	24/01/2025	Second Draft	Jaana Bäck (UH) Beñat Olascoaga (UH)
V 0.4	27/01/2025	Second Draft Revision	Klaus Steenberg Larsen (UCPH) Sabine Philippin (CNRS)
V 1.0	30/01/2025	Submitted version	Jaana Bäck (UH) Beñat Olascoaga (UH)

Document Description			
D3.1 IRISCC Training and Knowledge Exchange Plan			
Work Package Number 3			
Document Type	R - Document, report		
Document Status	Under EC Review	Version	v 1.0
Dissemination Level	Public		
Copyright Status	<p>This material by Parties of the IRISCC Consortium is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.</p>		
Lead partner	UH		
Document Link	https://www.iriscc.eu/publication/d3-1-IRISCC-training-and-knowledge-exchange-plan		
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.14777158		
Main Author(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jaana Bäck (UH) • Beñat Olascoaga (UH) 		
Contributing Authors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alexandre Belleflamme (FZJ) • Magdalena Brus (EGI.eu) • Yin Chen (EGI.eu) • Veronika Gaube (BOKU) • Päivi Haapanala (Luke) • Pasquale Pagano (CNR) • Christian Pagé (CERFCAS) • Mariana Salgado (ICOS ERIC) • Charles Troupin (ULiege) 		
Reviewers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Klaus Steenberg Larsen (UCPH) • Sabine Philippin (CNRS) 		
Approved by:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Noora Parre (Luke) 		
Estimated Delivery date	January 2025 (M10)		
Actual Delivery date	31/01/2025 (M10)		

Terminology / Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
CoS	Catalogue of Services
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
ENVRI	Environmental Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
IT	Information Technology
KE&T	Knowledge Exchange and Training
RI	Research Infrastructure
SDL	Service Design Lab
TA	Transnational Access
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
VA	Virtual Access
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

Executive summary	5
1 Introduction.....	6
1.1 Purpose and scope of the document	6
1.2 Knowledge exchange vs training	6
2 Activity audience.....	7
3 Activity medium	8
4 Activity timeline	8
5 Activity formats	10
5.1 Webinars	10
5.2 Tutorials, guides and infographics	10
5.3 Podcasts.....	10
5.4 Schools.....	11
5.5 Workshops.....	11
5.6 Hackathon	11
6 Activity objectives.....	12
7 Activity Prerequisites.....	13
8 Activity impact measures	14
9 Catalogue of activities.....	15
9.1 Knowledge exchange online activities	16
9.2 Training online activities	21
9.3 Training onsite activities	22
10 Sustainability of activities	26
11 Other catalogues of knowledge and training activities.....	26

Executive summary

This Deliverable D3.1 serves as the IRISCC project's training and knowledge exchange plan. The objective of the plan is to establish the roadmap for which knowledge and training needed to successfully exploit the services that the project produces, are facilitated and designed. The document is developed in collaboration with the project's service providers and users to consider and keep in mind their needs.

A stakeholder mapping and analysis has previously been completed and documented in the sensitive Deliverable D1.1: Stakeholder mapping and analysis, with the main outcomes being introduced in the public Deliverable D1.3: DEC Strategy. Five broad types of audiences have been identified in the context of the IRISCC project: research communities and networks, policy makers and implementation agencies, European Union (EU) project consortia, commercial users and societal users. In this respect, the plan includes a series of activities for different audiences, to facilitate the knowledge exchange and training in services that are designed to tackle risks induced and exacerbated by climate change. The proposed activities are further examined in terms of activity formats and activity media. For each of the planned activities, the objectives are described, a timeline is drawn, prerequisites are formulated and methods to measure the activity's impacts are stated.

The catalogue of activities presented in the plan can largely be classified in terms of knowledge exchange online activities (e.g. webinars, infographics, podcasts and tutorials) as well as training online (e.g. workshops) and onsite activities (e.g. workshops, hackathon and academic schools). Part of the training activities will focus on the use of virtual research environments, analytical tools and other methods that are relevant for the integration of the IRISCC services, showcased in the project by the IRISCC demonstrators. An additional part of the training will focus on socio-ecological tools and methods that are relevant for the co-designing of knowledge services, as showcased by the IRISCC service design labs.

The document is not meant to be a detailed and static plan. In this regard, activities included in this plan will be regularly monitored and reviewed over the lifetime of the project, to assess their impact and the appropriateness of their formats and media. IRISCC will closely collaborate with additional European Union-funded consortia and facilities (e.g. ENVRI-Hub NEXT and other projects supporting the ENVRI community) to explore synergies with their knowledge exchange and training plans.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope of the document

IRISCC aims to integrate climate change-related risk services and tools from 14 European research infrastructures (RIs) and facilities involved in the consortium. The consortium consists of a diverse array of observatories, experimental facilities, modelling capabilities and advanced data infrastructures, spanning environmental, social and computational sciences across various domains. The commonality behind such a diverse landscape is the work on climate risks, either by observing and recording, predicting and mitigating or adapting to the multitude of different climate change-related risks in different environments and contexts. Due to the multidisciplinary and transdisciplinary nature of the consortium, both IRISCC service providers and users are expected to have varying degrees of knowledge and skill capacities, which might be limiting for the optimal exploitation of the services and tools to be developed in the consortium.

The purpose of this document D3.1 is to create a roadmap to achieve the knowledge exchange and training (KE&T) capacity that is needed to successfully exploit the services developed by the IRISCC project in relation to risks associated with climate change. KE&T activities will be included as a service within the [Catalogue of Services](#) (CoS) of the project.

The scope of the KE&T plan is to develop a series of activities that are i) targeted to different service providing and service using audiences, ii) offered via the appropriate learning formats and media, iii) provided at a time within the project's lifetime that streamlines with IRISCC's relevant service releases and iv) are appropriate to measure the learning and training impacts.

1.2 Knowledge exchange vs training

The following plan draws a roadmap to deliver both the knowledge and training needed to successfully exploit the services developed in IRISCC. The plan makes a distinction between knowledge exchange and training, which comprise different aspects of the learning process.

Knowledge exchange is the transfer of information, which can deepen the familiarity, awareness and understanding of concepts and can potentially be interconnected with additional sources of information and concepts through experience and association. Knowledge exchange aims to create capacities for innovation and new knowledge, and develop intellectual capacity in a collaborative framework, together with other individuals who engage with the activities provided in the context of IRISCC. The transfer of good ideas, research results and skills as peer-to-peer learning to other RIs, businesses, the public sector and the wider community are all examples of knowledge exchange.

By **training**, the plan puts emphasis on the activities (e.g. hackathon, workshops and schools) where knowledge on use of concrete tools and methods is delivered to specific user groups. Training therefore is the aspect of the learning process that deals with the practical acquisition of skills and the use of those skills to create a desired outcome through practice.

Depending on the target audience and the identified objectives in the project, knowledge exchange activities will on certain occasions achieve the intended goals of the project, whilst in other cases training activities targeted to certain user groups will also be included for the successful exploitation of IRISCC services.

Due to the diversity of fields of knowledge and stakeholder groups within the IRISCC project, KE&T activities are to be tackled through the appropriate level of disciplinarity to successfully deliver the different services created in the consortium. Thus, whilst a **multidisciplinary** approach comprises the involvement of several discrete, within-boundaries disciplines to address a common topic or service, an **interdisciplinary** approach addresses the topic as a combined, interdependent entity that incorporates all involved disciplines. For the case of some topics and services, KE&T activities might require of a **transdisciplinary** approach, characterised by the merging of all involved disciplines beyond their within-discipline boundaries and thus developing a novel framework to address the challenge at hand.

2 Activity audience

As identified in Deliverable D1.1: Stakeholder Mapping and Analysis, five broad groups of stakeholders have been recognised in the context of the IRISCC project: research communities and networks, policy makers and implementation agencies, EU projects consortia, commercial users and societal users. Nevertheless, not all types of audience need the same level of knowledge and training, as not all audiences have the same level of interest or impact on the project.

Additionally, it has been identified in Deliverable D1.2: DEC Strategy, that for the case of work package (WP) 3, RIs and scientists on environmental research represent audiences of high interest and high impact for the project, followed by experts on training activities and

ultimately the broader research community, with high interest yet low influence capacity. For the cases of WP2 and WP5, policy makers from local to supra-national levels have been identified to be audiences of high interest and impact, followed by experts in their respective fields of Service Design Labs (SDLs) and eventually additional policy makers and researchers not involved in the IRISCC project, who have high interest yet low influence.

It is in this regard that training activities will be targeted mainly to **research communities and networks**, whilst knowledge exchange activities will not only include research-related audiences but will also accommodate **policy makers** as well as **commercial and societal users**.

3 Activity medium

A wide variety of learning activities can be facilitated **online**. A clear benefit of online learning is that online activities can reach a wider audience, as they are not limited to a given time, space and location. Unlike onsite learning, online learning activities further facilitate the sustainability of the project, as all learning material can be stored, revisited and used beyond the lifetime of the project. As stated in Deliverable D1.2: DEC Strategy, the IRISCC project will also develop a dedicated YouTube channel, in which video content produced during the project's lifetime will be made available to the general public.

Under certain circumstances in which an in-depth skill knowledge needs to be developed or further enhanced, topic-specific knowledge and skill development opportunities will also be offered as **onsite** training activities. To promote onsite training sustainability, learning material associated to onsite trainings will also be made available online. Onsite activities will be addressed through a **blended learning** approach, in which an online available part of the training will be required to be performed in addition to the activities onsite. Additionally, certain activities might be offered through a **hybrid** medium, combining both online and onsite audiences.

4 Activity timeline

To get the maximum impact from KE&T events, the activities will be streamlined with the three **service releases** planned in the IRISCC project (Figure 1). The first service release, planned for March 2025, consists of the publication of the IRISCC CoS, which compiles the existing services from the 14 RIs involved in the consortium. Training activities for service providers as well as knowledge exchange activities for the research community and networks will be facilitated during this stage, to ensure the successful release of the catalogue and the implementation of calls for virtual-(VA) and transnational access (TA) to the RI services.

Figure 1. The three IRISCC service releases and the associated stakeholders per service release

The second service release, planned for September 2026, aims for the integration of the previous services, and will exhibit their integrative potential by showcasing six climate change-related risk-specific study cases, namely **demonstrators**. These demonstrators will explore risks i) on human health in urban areas during heatwaves associated with deteriorated air quality, ii) in coastal regions due to flooding caused by sea-level rise and storm surges, iii) on terrestrial ecosystems functioning and services due to droughts and heatwaves, iv) on marine ecosystems biodiversity, functioning and services caused by ocean acidification, warming and deoxygenation, v) on food security due to multi-hazard risks and vi) on multiple systems due to wildfires in Europe. Training of relevant tools and knowledge exchange activities for the research community and networks will be facilitated during this stage to ensure the successful integration of climate-change risk services and the pertinent calls for VA and TA to the services.

The last service release, planned for March 2028, focuses on the co-design of knowledge services, and showcases four climate change-related, risk-specific topic cases, namely **Service Design Labs (SDLs)**. The objectives of these SDLs will be i) the creation of a land-use decision-making SDL, ii) a case-specific evaluation and adaptation of mitigation actions to drought, iii) the creation of a soil carbon SDL and iv) the co-designing of a SDL along with various types of stakeholders. At this stage, socio-ecological training activities as well as knowledge exchange activities will be facilitated for a wider range of audiences beyond the research community.

Thus, over the lifetime of the project and following the three service releases, the target audiences for KE&T activities will expand from the research community and networks to further include policy makers as well as commercial and societal users.

5 Activity formats

The diversity in the types of audience and learning media requires varying learning formats to reach the target stakeholders and KE&T objectives. The activity formats included in the KE&T plan consist of webinars, tutorials, guides and infographics, podcasts, academic schools, workshops and a hackathon.

5.1 Webinars

Also known as online seminars or web-based lectures, webinars are online topic-specific lessons imparted in real-time to an attending audience. Webinars allow the spread of information from a general introductory level to a more advanced level. WP3 along with WPI will produce a series of webinars with the following themes relevant to IRISCC services: demonstrators, SDLs, RIs, IRISCC CoS, data stewardship and virtual research environment (VRE) platforms.

5.2 Tutorials, guides and infographics

In the case of complex and extensive information about the IRISCC services and climate risks, such information can be made more accessible and engaging by using collections of infographics and visualisations. Infographics as well as guiding and tutorial material can also be produced online and be designed to reach a broader, general audience.

Additionally, tutorials and guides can also make the spread of information and instructions to be more straightforward and understandable even for project-internal actors, for instance by creating tutorials for IRISCC service providers on how to populate the catalogue of services.

5.3 Podcasts

Podcasts are digital audio files available online and often exploring varying topics by means of a series of topic-specific episodes. The podcast has been identified as an innovative communication tool with capacity to engage with a broad audience and therefore raise awareness about the IRISCC mission and services.

The podcast “Diseño y Diáspora” (i.e. Spanish for “Design and Diaspora”), which focuses on social design, has collaborated with the IRISCC project to produce a series centred on **Infrastructures**. The series comprises five episodes that explore the intersection between

design and infrastructure, and it also includes infrastructures beyond scientific, research purposes.

The podcast features interviews with experts from various fields, offering insights into how design can enhance the efficiency, user-friendliness and impact of infrastructures. Hosted by Mariana Salgado, co-lead for WP2 and contributor to stakeholder engagement activities in WPI, the series delves into these critical themes. Should IRISCC decide to create additional podcast content, we will thoughtfully design how these materials can be integrated into IRISCC training programs.

5.4 Schools

Summer and winter schools are short-term, often residential, academic courses aimed to fully immerse the participant in a specific study topic. Academic schools are quite often delivered onsite and combine a series of lectures along with hands-on training activities and site visits. They are normally arranged to target an audience with previous knowledge and training on the study topic at hand, yet willing to expand them further on. Three academic schools are planned to be arranged over the IRISCC project's lifetime.

5.5 Workshops

Workshops comprise a more interactive, hands-on and participatory learning approach than seminars and webinars, promoting discussion and encouraging learning, collaborating and problem-solving. Workshops can be delivered either online, onsite or on a hybrid format. Yet, the type of audience in workshops does not tend to be as general and wide as in seminars and webinars, being an audience with a deeper knowledge and stronger interest on the topic at hand.

5.6 Hackathon

A hackathon represents an intense yet time-bound event, in which participants collaborate with the aim to solve a given challenge. This type of activity is often created either online or in a hybrid format, it may contain knowledge exchange and training and is normally targeted to audiences with a pre-established level of relevant knowledge and skills to succeed in the task.

Hackathons can help participants develop skills such as problem solving, critical thinking, creativity, teamwork, communication and time management. Hackathons can also lead to the creation of innovative solutions to real-world challenges and promote community building around a particular technology.

During the lifetime of the project, a hackathon will be arranged, with the theme of the hackathon to be developed together with WPI and several other WPs. Additionally, participants will have the opportunity to test the project's services and tools, providing valuable feedback on aspects such as functionality, user interface (UI) and user experience (UX). This input will be instrumental in refining and improving the services, ensuring they better meet user needs.

6 Activity objectives

All the objectives of KE&T activities are centred around the effective sharing of information, skills and expertise to exploit the IRISCC services as well as foster growth, innovation and development. The core objectives behind the KE&T activities are:

Improving skills and competencies

Training activities can help participants to acquire new capabilities or upgrade existing ones, leading to the individual's improved performance and productivity. Enhancing the knowledge and skill capacity of IRISCC participants enables them to perform better in their current roles and can also encourage them to take new responsibilities.

Fostering collaboration and networking

The activities proposed in the plan can facilitate the exchange of ideas, experiences and best practices among participants. In turn, they can create opportunities for collaboration, innovation and learning from different perspectives, leading to stronger networks and partnerships.

Facilitating knowledge transfer and innovation

Ensuring that knowledge is transferred and exchanged among participants and different audiences can harness the collective knowledge within the consortium and further encourage innovations and continuous improvement.

Increasing the effectiveness in policy or practice implementation

The dissemination of knowledge and skills, targeted not only to specific IRISCC stakeholders but to the whole set of stakeholders and even wider audiences, can support the implementation of initiatives and policies, and help to improve decision-making. Training can facilitate the translation of complex research results and knowledge into actionable strategies. The dissemination of knowledge and skills can also lead to a more successful implementation of strategies, as they ensure that goals are met, and best practices are followed.

Empowering participants and audiences

Activities related to KE&T can build the confidence and self-efficacy of participants, as they empower individuals with the necessary knowledge and skills. Empowering participants

and audiences can also enhance teamwork and promote a sense of ownership in their roles.

Promoting continuous learning and development

The activities proposed in the plan help the participant to stay up to date with the relevant knowledge, tools and technologies concerning IRISCC-related topics. The process of continuous learning and development encourages a culture of lifelong learning, which is crucial for staying competitive and adaptable to changing circumstances.

Building a knowledge-sharing culture

One of the objectives of learning activities is to create a community who values and prioritises the exchange of information and collaboration. A knowledge-sharing working culture ensures the participant's continued growth and benefits all members within and beyond the IRISCC consortium.

Encouraging diversity of thought

Some of the activities on the KE&T plan are meant to combine different types of audience and therefore promote the sharing of ideas from diverse sources and points of view, which can enhance problem-solving and decision-making processes. Diverse perspectives lead to more creative solutions, fostering in turn inclusive and innovative environments.

Facilitating user interaction and service improvement

Training activities provide a valuable opportunity for engaging directly with users. These sessions not only enhance knowledge and skills but also serve as a platform to gather feedback on IRISCC services, tools and resources. By understanding user experiences and perspectives, the consortium can identify areas for improvement in functionality, usability and overall service design, ensuring that the offerings better align with the needs of the community. This interactive exchange fosters a collaborative environment where users feel heard and valued.

7 Activity Prerequisites

Due to the educational and informative nature of the activities related with knowledge exchange, there is no foreseen prerequisites for such activities, as the facilitated information can be adjusted based on the format (e.g. webinars and infographics) and audience type (e.g. research community and general public).

Training activities might require the participant to be familiar to a certain level with certain concepts, knowledge or tools in relation to the training. For instance, training activities aimed to further exploit certain software and additional tools would require that the participant has a basic topic-specific knowledge as well as familiarity with certain programming languages (e.g. Python or Linux) and computing platforms (e.g. Jupyter

notebook) to succeed in the training. Alternatively, additional training events might need specific research and technology prerequisites.

8 Activity impact measures

Impact measures help evaluate the effectiveness of the IRISCC activities designed to share, disseminate, apply and further develop IRISCC-specific knowledge. These measures aim to assess both the short- and long-term effects of KE&T on individual users, organisations and communities within the IRISCC consortium as well as at broader public bodies and communities.

Individual impacts can be linked to actions demonstrating how well the knowledge has been shared and whether it is effectively applied in practice. They can also be assessed by exploring the contribution of IRISCC knowledge exchange to fostering innovation and generating new ideas, solutions or behavioural changes.

Community impacts can be assessed by scrutinising how knowledge exchange activities have facilitated new collaborations and expanded professional networks within and beyond the IRISCC consortium, by analysing their impacts on the overall organisation performance and the creation of novel services at the RIs (including productivity, quality and efficiency) or by monitoring the capacity of organisations to tackle challenges and seize opportunities in additional relevant topics.

The **broader public impacts** manifest themselves in financial or operational return relative to the investments made in KE&T activities, and in the enhanced sustainability of the knowledge exchange impact over time and its corresponding long-term benefits. The level of satisfaction, the level of engagement of key stakeholders involved and the impacts of KE&T on the organisation or community culture are examples of central impact measures.

Many of the abovementioned impacts differ in their lifetimes, with some of the impacts with environmental and societal value most likely manifesting beyond the project's lifetime (and thus making their verification difficult). Within the IRISCC's lifetime, short- and medium-term impacts of KE&T activities can still be measured through an array of quantitative and qualitative metrics. Among the quantitative metrics to measure the impact, the project can for instance quantify the participation (e.g. number of activity attendants), engagement level (e.g. activity retention time) and feedback from participants. Qualitative feedback on usability and satisfaction, collected from activity attendants, can be analysed and consequently used as metrics for the impact of the IRISCC KE&T activities.

9 Catalogue of activities

Many of the activities had previously been listed in the project proposal and further described in the project’s Grant Agreement. This plan further documents and extends the catalogue of activities with the current information available. We present the following concrete KE&T activities, grouped in terms of activity media and formats, and identify their target audiences, timings, objectives, prerequisites and impact measures. Reports on the training activities (i.e. Deliverables D3.2 and D3.3, M24 and M50) and the hackathon (i.e. Deliverable D3.4, M52) will also be delivered during the project’s lifetime.

Figure 2. Training activities included in the KE&T plan and their timings over the whole lifetime of the IRISCC project and in relation to the three service releases.

9.1 Knowledge exchange online activities

IRISCC will create a collection of thematic series of webinars (Table 1) with the objective to inform and educate the research community participating or interested in the project about topics relevant to the IRISCC services. A total of six thematic series of webinars will be produced. A series of webinars will focus on the IRISCC CoS, demonstrating how to navigate the catalogue, introducing its available services and explaining how to access RIs virtually, physically and remotely. Additional thematic series of webinars will introduce the users to i) RIs, ii) D4Science VRE, iii) data stewardship, iv) demonstrators and v) SDLs developed in IRISCC. Webinars will be offered over the entire duration of the IRISCC project and will be streamlined with the service release events.

Table 1. Information on the theme-specific series of webinars as part of the KE&T plan for IRISCC service providers and users.

Webinars	
1. Webinar: The IRISCC Catalogue of Services (CoS)	
Audience	Research community
Timing	Summer 2025
Objectives	To: facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-exchange culture
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of webinar attendants, Attendant engagement, Attending time, Number of webinar viewers, Viewer engagement
2. Webinar: Research Infrastructures (RIs) in IRISCC	
Audience	Research community
Timing	Summer - Autumn 2025
Objectives	To: facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-exchange culture
Prerequisites	None

Impact measures	Number of webinar attendants, Attendant engagement, Attending time, Number of webinar viewers, Viewer engagement
3. Webinar: The D4Science Virtual Research Environment (VRE)	
Audience	Research community
Timing	Autumn 2025
Objectives	To: facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-exchange culture
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of webinar attendants, Attendant engagement, Attending time, Number of webinar viewers, Viewer engagement
4. Webinar: Data stewardship	
Audience	Research community
Timing	Autumn 2025 – Winter 2026
Objectives	To: facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-exchange culture
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of webinar attendants, Attendant engagement, Attending time, Number of webinar viewers, Viewer engagement
5. Webinar: IRISCC demonstrators	
Audience	Research community
Timing	Spring – Summer 2026
Objectives	To: facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-exchange culture
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of webinar attendants, Attendant engagement, Attending time, Number of webinar viewers, Viewer engagement
6. Webinar: IRISCC Service Design Labs (SDLs)	
Audience	Research community

Timing	Spring – Summer 2028
Objectives	To: facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-exchange culture
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of webinar attendants, Attendant engagement, Attending time, Number of webinar viewers, Viewer engagement

Additionally, a virtual tour to the IRISCC CoS (Table 2) will also be created to introduce the project and its services to a broader audience. Similarly, tutorials for IRISCC users, providers and reviewers in relation to TA calls will also be facilitated. Infographics concerning the RIs involved in IRISCC as well as the demonstrators and SDLs developed during the project’s lifetime will also be produced for informative purposes.

Table 2. Information on the guides relevant to IRISCC service providers and users, as part of the KE&T plan.

Tutorials, guides and infographics	
1. Tutorial: IRISCC CoS virtual tour	
Audience	Research community, Policy makers, Commercial users, Societal users
Timing	Spring 2025
Objectives	To: facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-sharing culture
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of viewings, Feedback
2. Tutorial: Applying for transnational access for IRISCC users	
Audience	Research community, Policy makers, Commercial users, Societal users
Timing	Summer 2025
Objectives	To: facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-sharing culture
Prerequisites	None

Impact measures	Number of viewings, Feedback
3. Tutorial: Evaluating transnational access applications for IRISCC providers	
Audience	Research community, Policy makers, Commercial users, Societal users
Timing	Summer – Autumn 2025
Objectives	To: facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-sharing culture
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of viewings, Feedback
4. Tutorial: Peer-reviewing transnational access applications for IRISCC reviewers	
Audience	Research community, Policy makers, Commercial users, Societal users
Timing	Summer – Autumn 2025
Objectives	To: facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-sharing culture
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of viewings, Feedback
5. Infographic: IRISCC RIs	
Audience	Research community, Policy makers, Commercial users, Societal users
Timing	Autumn 2025
Objectives	To: facilitate knowledge transfer, build a knowledge-sharing culture
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of downloads
6. Infographic: IRISCC demonstrators	
Audience	Research community, Policy makers, Commercial users, Societal users

Timing	Summer 2026
Objectives	To: facilitate knowledge transfer, build a knowledge-sharing culture
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of downloads
7. Infographic: IRISCC SDLs	
Audience	Research community, Policy makers, Commercial users, Societal users
Timing	Summer 2028
Objectives	To: facilitate knowledge transfer, build a knowledge-sharing culture
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of downloads

An alternative to screen-dependent formats with the objective to inform the general public about the IRISCC project's mission and services will be implemented via podcasts (Table 3).

Table 3. Information on the series of podcasts as part of the KE&T plan for IRISCC service providers and users.

Podcasts	
1. Podcast series: Infrastructures	
Audience	Research community, Policy makers, Commercial users, Societal users
Timing	Winter 2024
Objectives	To: facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, build a knowledge-sharing culture, encourage diversity of thought
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of listeners, Number of downloads, Listener retention time, Feedback

9.2 Training online activities

Training activities related to software, methodologies and tools relevant to the successful exploitation of IRISCC services, demonstrators and SDLs will also be facilitated over the project lifetime and streamlined so that they maximise the impact of the three IRISCC service releases (Figure 2).

Some of the training will be facilitated as online workshops (Table 4), some as onsite workshops (Table 5) and some other training activities will be included as part of three academic schools (Table 6).

Table 4. Information on the theme-specific online workshops as part of the KE&T plan for IRISCC service providers and users.

Workshops (online)	
1. Online workshop: Populating the IRISCC CoS	
Audience	Service providers
Timing	Winter 2025
Objectives	To: foster collaboration, facilitate knowledge transfer, build a knowledge-sharing culture
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of participants, Participant engagement, Number of entries
2. Online workshop: Coastal Flood Impact Analyser	
Audience	Research community
Timing	Autumn 2026
Objectives	To: improve skills, foster collaboration, facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, build a knowledge-sharing culture
Prerequisites	Basic knowledge in Python, Basic knowledge in Jupyter notebook
Impact measures	Number of participants, Number of demonstrator users, User engagement, Feedback
3. Online workshop: IS-ENES Virtual Research Environment (VRE)	

Audience	Research community
Timing	Winter 2028
Objectives	To: improve skills, foster collaboration, facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, build knowledge-sharing culture
Prerequisites	Knowledge in Python
Impact measures	Number of participants, Participant engagement, Participant retention rate, Feedback

9.3 Training onsite activities

Table 5. Information on the theme-specific onsite workshops as part of the KE&T plan for IRISCC service providers and users.

Workshops (onsite)	
1. Onsite workshop: FitSM IT service management	
Audience	Research Infrastructures
Timing	Autumn 2025 (onsite)/Summer 2026 (onsite)/ Spring 2027 (online) (tentative timings. The training is offered at least once, but can be repeated if in demand)
Objectives	To: improve skills
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of participants, Participant engagement, Feedback
2. Onsite workshop: Data Interpolating Variational Analysis (DIVAnd) software tool	
Audience	Research community
Timing	Autumn 2025
Objectives	To: improve skills, facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-sharing culture
Prerequisites	Basic programming knowledge

Impact measures	Number of participants, Participant engagement, Feedback
3. Onsite workshop: Integrated framework to assess climate change risks	
Audience	Research community
Timing	Spring 2026
Objectives	To: improve skills, foster collaboration, facilitate knowledge transfer, increase the effectiveness in policy and practice implementation, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-sharing culture, encourage diversity of thought
Prerequisites	Background on interdisciplinary research, Background on social sciences, Basic knowledge on transdisciplinary research
Impact measures	Number of participants, Participant engagement, Feedback
4. Onsite workshop: Socio-ecological tools for stakeholder engagement	
Audience	Research community
Timing	Spring 2027
Objectives	To: improve skills, foster collaboration, facilitate knowledge transfer, increase the effectiveness in policy and practice implementation, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-sharing culture, encourage diversity of thought
Prerequisites	Background on interdisciplinary research, Background on social sciences, Basic knowledge on transdisciplinary research
Impact measures	Number of participants, Participant engagement, Feedback

Table 6. Information on the theme-specific summer and autumn academic schools as part of the KE&T plan for IRISCC service providers and users.

Summer and autumn schools	
1. Autumn school: High-performance scientific computing in terrestrial systems (HPSC TerrSys)	
Audience	Research community
Timing	Autumn 2025
Objectives	To: improve skills, facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-sharing culture
Prerequisites	Knowledge in Linux command line, Knowledge in geosciences
Impact measures	Number of participants, Feedback
2. Summer school: Climate risks data analysis tools and methods	
Audience	Research community
Timing	Summer 2026
Objectives	To: improve skills, facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-sharing culture
Prerequisites	Knowledge in Python, Knowledge in Jupyter Lab, Knowledge in climate science
Impact measures	Number of participants, Feedback
3. Summer school: Data science for climate risks	
Audience	Research community
Timing	Summer 2027
Objectives	To: improve skills, facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, promote continuous learning, build a knowledge-sharing culture

Prerequisites	Knowledge in Python, Knowledge in Jupyter Lab, Knowledge in climate science
Impact measures	Number of participants, Feedback

IRISCC will also host a hackathon event (Table 7). This hackathon will serve to advertise and exploit the already developed IRISCC services, and its objective will be to engage researchers and users in hands-on problem-solving activities that test the usability, functionality and relevance of the services and tools developed within the project.

Participants will have the opportunity to explore these services in depth, provide valuable feedback on their user experience (e.g. UI/UX improvements to CoS) and suggest enhancements based on practical applications. The event will focus on fostering innovation by encouraging participants to develop creative solutions to real-world challenges using IRISCC services.

In addition, the hackathon aims to build a collaborative community around the services by connecting users, researchers and stakeholders, promoting knowledge exchange and nurturing transdisciplinary partnerships.

Table 7. Information on the hackathon as part of the KE&T plan for IRISCC service providers and users.

Hackathon	
1. Hackathon: RiskHack	
Audience	Research community, Data scientists, Developers
Timing	Summer 2026
Objectives	To: improve skills and competencies, foster collaboration, facilitate knowledge transfer, empower participants/audiences, build a knowledge-sharing culture, encourage diversity of thought, facilitate user interaction and service improvement
Prerequisites	None
Impact measures	Number of participants, Number of services, Diversity of participants (e.g. research fields, regions and expertise), Community engagement, Participant satisfaction score, Feedback collected, Implemented improvements

10 Sustainability of activities

The sustainability of IRISCC's knowledge exchange program is connected to the overall sustainability of IRISCC's services provisioning and refers to the ability to maintain long-term benefits and continue to deliver value for its user communities over time. It ensures that the exchange of knowledge remains relevant, effective and impactful in the long-term, whilst adapting to the changing needs of its users. A sustainable KE&T program will require a careful planning, resource management and the ongoing engagement of the service providers.

11 Other catalogues of knowledge and training activities

Apart from the activities listed in this plan, IRISCC will advocate for the continuous learning on climate change-related risks by closely collaborating with additional EU-funded consortia and facilities (e.g. ENVRI-Hub NEXT, AgroServ, AQUASERV, and other projects supporting the ENVRI community) to explore synergies with their KE&T catalogues.